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ASSOCIATION OF ARTIFICIAL POISON AS *DUSHIVISHA* IN THE MANIFESTATION OF *VICHARCHIKA* AND *DADRU* - A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Nowadays, the prevalence of skin diseases has increased significantly due to altered lifestyles, consumption of incompatible foods, synthetic additives in foods, prolonged exposure to unhealthy environmental conditions, pesticides, industrial chemicals, heavy metals, and household products. In Ayurveda this concept can be correlated with *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha*. *Dushivisha* is the poison that vitiates the Dhatus frequently when exposed to a particular place, time, food, and day sleep. These poisons remain dormant in the body for long periods, disrupting normal physiological functions and contributing to the development of various diseases, including skin disorders such as *Vicharchika* (Eczema) and *Dadru* (Tinea infections). **Objective:** To evaluate the association of exposure of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* with *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* through an observational study. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was designed wherein 300 participants were interviewed personally from December 2023 to August 2024. The participants were selected using non-randomized convenience sampling for this study. Ethical clearance was obtained from Institute and a research proforma was used for survey study which is documented all possible *Nidanas* of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics. Data was arranged into 2 × 2 table and odd ratio was calculated for each *Nidana* of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha*. **Results:** Odds ratio for the association between the exposure to artificial poison v/s *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru*, *Viruddhahara* v/s *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* with 95% Confidence interval were found 7.375(4.39- 12.37), 4.992(3.05- 8.16) respectively. **Conclusion:** Study reveals that a significant association between exposure of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* with *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* and can be concluded that *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* plays a major role in the skin disorders such as *Vicharchika* (Eczema) and *Dadru* (Tinea infections).

Key Words:

Dushivisha, *Vicharchika*, *Dadru*, *Kritrim Visha*, Artificial poison

INTRODUCTION:

In the present era, various factors contribute to the development of diseases in humans, with *Dushivisha* being a significant cause. *Dushivisha* refers to a toxin derived from inanimate (*Sthavara*) or animate (*Jangama*) sources, or even artificial toxins (*Kritrim Visha*), which, after partial elimination from the body through detoxification with anti-poisonous drugs, remains lodged in body tissues as latent poison. Under favourable conditions, this latent poison triggers the aggravation of *Doshas*, vitiates *Dhatus*, and leads to the manifestation of diseases. Unlike acute poisons, *Dushi Visha* lacks the ten classical properties of poison, making it less potent. However, it exerts a delayed and cumulative toxic effect on the body without typically causing immediate fatality.¹

With changing lifestyles, individuals are increasingly exposed to various types of toxins in their daily lives through food, beverages, medications, environmental pollutants, and other sources. This concept can be effectively correlated with the concept of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as described in classical Ayurvedic literature. Acharya Sushruta stated that *Kushtha* (skin diseases) are one among the major manifestations of *Dushivisha*.² Also, Acharya Charaka asserts that *Dushivisha* vitiates *Rakta Dhatu* and causes various skin lesions such as *Aru*, *Koth* and *Kitibha* kind of *Kushtha*.³ By exposing on self to *Kritrima Visha* human beings unknowingly invited number of various diseases, including skin disorders such as *Vicharchika* (Eczema) and *Dadru* (Tinea infections). *Vicharchika* and *Dadru* are highly prevalent diseases in the survey region and are commonly treated at I.T.R.A. hospital, therefore selected as outcome of interest.

Aim and objectives:

To evaluate the association of exposure of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* with *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* through observational study.

Materials and methods:

Cross-sectional survey study was conducted among 300 participants from Jamnagar and its periphery regions. Participants were selected on the basis of non-randomized convenience sampling from the period of December 2023 to August 2024. Ethical clearance was obtained for this study from Institutional Ethics Committee. (PGT/7/-A/Ethics/2023- 24/233 dated 01/04/2024).

Selection of the participants:

Diagnosed cases of *Vicharchika* and *Dadru* were selected from the OPD of the department of Agad Tantra and referred from other O.P.Ds, ITRA, Jamnagar.

Number of participants:

A total of 300 participants were selected for the survey study, on the basis of outcome of interest, divided into two groups: the diseased group and the non-diseased group. In the diseased group, diagnosed cases of *Vicharchika* and *Dadru* were selected. In the non-diseased group, participants were not having any skin diseases, decided as a comparator group. Written informed consent from all the participants was obtained after explaining the details of the study and its aims.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Any person (either patient or his/her relative) attending ITRA hospital.
- Age between 18 – 60 years, irrespective of gender, occupation, caste or social economic status.
- Patients ready to enroll in the study with written consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Participants having sign, symptoms, or diseases mentioned in classical texts for *Dushivisha* excepts outcome of interest such as ascites, insanity, oligospermia.
- Mentally unstable or not responsive.
- Terminally ill patients.

Preparation of proforma:

A specialized research proforma was designed to record participants demographic data, lifestyle, and potential *Nidanas* of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* through open- and closed-ended questionnaires. Participants were screened for inclusion and subjected to interviews and examinations based on the validated questionnaire, considering exposure and outcomes. Data were documented from a single interviewer in a language comfortable to the participants, integrating both modern and Ayurvedic perspectives.

Criteria of Assessment:

Exposure Assessment (History of Artificial poison):

1. History of Artificial poison:

Industrial exposure includes hazardous gases, fumes, corrosives, irritants, and cement, which contribute to toxin accumulation in the body. Additionally, addiction to substances such as smoking, tobacco, alcohol, tea, and coffee further increases toxic exposure. Medication use, excluding over-the-counter drugs, is another factor, categorized based on duration as short-term (<1 month), moderate (1–3 months), sub-chronic (1–3 years), and chronic (>3 years). Agricultural exposure primarily involves pesticides and chemicals, while household poisons, including insecticides, mothballs, furniture polish, cleaners, dish and laundry detergents, and bleach, also contribute to toxin accumulation.

2. History of Viruddhahara:

A detailed questionnaire with 25 questions assessed *Viruddhahara* sevana based on frequency and duration. Exposure levels were categorized as Rarely (1-2 times/month), Occasionally (1 time/week), Frequently (2-5 days/week), and Daily (6-7 days/week). Consumption of four types of food items occasionally, three frequently, or one daily was considered a history of *Viruddhahara*.

Statistical Analysis:

After collection of data, the statistical calculations were done with the help of IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 software. The data was presented in 2 × 2 table for each *Nidana* of

Kritrima Visha (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha*. The Odds ratio test was applied to evaluate the association between exposure to *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* and the outcomes (*Vicharchika* & *Dadru*). Confidence interval (CI) (95%) was also analyzed to observe that data was whether statistically significant or not.

Results:

A total of 300 participants were interviewed for the survey study based on the outcome of interest. The majority included 25.66% of participants with *Dadru* and 24.33% with *Vicharchika* who exhibited the outcome of interest [Table 1]. Among them, 41.10% of participants with *Vicharchika* had a chronic history of 1–3 years, while 53.25% of participants with *Dadru* had a chronicity of less than one year [Table 2].

The Odds ratio of 3.020 for *Vicharchika*, for the exposed group compared with unexposed group indicates moderate significant association between artificial poison and *Vicharchika*. The 95% C.I. (1.74- 5.23) indicates that result is statistically significant because it doesn't contain 1 [Table 3]. 2.353 Odds ratio for *Vicharchika* calculated based on the number of exposed and unexposed participants for *Viruddhahara* in the whole population. The 95% C.I. (1.35- 4.11) indicates that the result is statistically significant because it doesn't contain 1 [Table 4].

For *Dadru*, Odds ratio of 4.025, for the exposed group compared with unexposed group indicates strongly association between artificial poison and outcome *Dadru*. The 95% C.I. (2.31- 7.01) indicates that result is statistically significant because it doesn't contain 1 [Table 5]. An Odds ratio of 3.687 for *Dadru* was calculated based on the number of exposed and unexposed participants in the entire population. The 95% C.I. (2.06-6.6) indicates that the result is statistically significant because it doesn't contain 1 [Table 6]. Odds ratio of 7.375 for *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru*, for the exposed group compared with unexposed group indicates strongly association between artificial poison and *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru*. The 95% C.I. (4.39- 12.37) indicates that the result is statistically significant because it doesn't contain 1 [Table 7]. 4.992 Odds ratio for *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* calculated based on the number of exposed and unexposed participants in the whole population. The 95% C.I. (3.05 – 8.16) indicates that the result is statistically significant because it doesn't contain 1 [Table 8].

Tables

Table 1: Status of outcome wise distribution in 300 participants

Status of outcome	Number of participants (N)	Percentage (%)
<i>Vicharchika</i>	73	24.33%
<i>Dadru</i>	77	25.66%
Total	300	100%

Table 2: Chronicity of disease wise distribution (in diseased group)

Chronicity of Vicharchikal/ Dadru	No. of participants with Vicharchika (N)	Percentage (%)	No. of participants with Dadru (N)	Percentage (%)
<1 Year	23	31.50%	41	53.25%
1-3 Year	30	41.10%	24	31.15%
>3 Year	20	27.40%	12	15.60%
Total	73	100%	77	100%

Table 3: Association between Artificial poison v/s Vicharchika

Artificial poison	Vicharchika		Total No. of Participants
	Yes	No	
Exposed group	47	85	132
Non-exposed group	26	142	168
Total No. of Participants	73	227	300

Table 4: Association between Viruddhahara v/s Vicharchika

Viruddhahara	Vicharchika		Total No. of Participants
	Yes	No	
Exposed group	50	109	159
Non-exposed group	23	118	141
Total No. of Participants	73	227	300

Table 5: Association between Artificial poison v/s Dadru

Artificial poison	Dadru		Total No. of Participants
	Yes	No	
Exposed group	53	79	132
Non-exposed group	24	144	168
Total No. of Participants	77	223	300

Table 6: Association between *Viruddhahara* v/s *Dadru*

<i>Viruddhahara</i>	<i>Dadru</i>		Total No. of Participants
	Yes	No	
Exposed group	58	101	159
Non-exposed group	19	122	141
Total No. of Participants	77	223	300

Table 7: Association between Artificial poison v/s *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru*

Artificial poison	<i>Vicharchika</i> and/or <i>Dadru</i>		Total No. of Participants
	Yes	No	
Exposed group	100	32	132
Non-exposed group	50	118	168
Total No. of Participants	150	150	300

Table 8: Association between *Viruddhahara* v/s *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru*

<i>Viruddhahara</i>	<i>Vicharchika</i> and/or <i>Dadru</i>		Total No. of Participants
	Yes	No	
Exposed group	108	51	159
Non-exposed group	42	99	141
Total No. of Participants	150	150	300

Discussion:

In the current scenario, there are many different ways that poisons can be exposed to people, including pesticides, fertilizers, medicines, metals & minerals, food preservatives, adulteration, colouring agents, industrial exposure to various chemicals, etc. In Ayurveda this concept can be correlated with *Kritima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha*. *Dushivisha* stays in the body by getting *Aavruta* by *Kapha* and similarly dominance of *Kapha Dosha* is seen in *Vicharchika* and *Dadru* according to different classics. In both *Dushivisha* as well as *Vicharchika* and *Dadru*, the recurring and relapsing tendency is seen under favorable conditions such as *Dushita Desa*, *Dushita Kala*, *Dushita Anna*, and *Divaswapna*⁴. Kriyakoumudi lists additional *Nidanas* of *Dushivisha*, beyond those found in Bruhatrayi, including the consumption of *Asatmya Dravya*, *Adhyashana*, *Viruddhashana*, *Ajeernashana*, Various Roganu and

Anunashak Aushadha. This can be interpreted as the effects of microbes, along with the use of various antibiotics or steroids for treatment. Furthermore, the retention of metabolic waste products such as *Purisha*, *Mutra* and *Artava* can transform into *Dushivisha*, as these toxic substances are reabsorbed into the body.⁵

Cross-sectional studies can be susceptible to certain types of biases and confounding factors, and it is important to consider these potential limitations and address them through proper population selection and survey design. One common type of bias is selection bias. In selecting a study population, the sample should be representative of the general population in terms of exposure probabilities. If the controls (unexposed) in the study are not appropriately selected for analytical study, the results may either underestimate or overestimate the true associations. Recall bias can also be a concern, particularly when surveys are used to collect data. In cross-sectional studies, individuals may report their exposures differently, leading to discrepancies between exposed and unexposed group. If exposed group tend to recall their exposures more extensively than unexposed, the study results could be biased, overestimating the effect. To minimize selection bias, his/ her relatives were chosen for the survey study as unexposed group.

In the diseased group maximum, i.e., 26.67% participants were housewives, followed by other work (like carpenter, painter, shop-keeper) 25.33%, labour (12.67%), industrial (11.33%). This reflects the fact that most of the participants were housewives, 26.67%, housewives are more likely to come into contact with irritating substances in household articles, such as dish wash, detergents, floor cleaning agents, and so on. Since, the site of participant selection is an industrial area, 11.33% of participants were industrial workers, who may often come into contact with irritating substances. Out of 300 participants, 159 participants were having exposure to *Viruddhahara*, followed by addiction in 107 participants, history of medications (apart from OTC) in 52 participants, industrial exposure to chemicals in 34 participants, household poisons in 15 participants, followed by pesticides in 3 participants. In participants with addiction, 50% use tobacco. This is because the consumption of tobacco is more at the site of participant selection. Medications on long term use lead to toxic effects that gradually accumulate in the body and serve as a contributing factor of *Dushivisha*. In the present study, among industrial chemicals, more exposure was observed with irritants, and others (oils, etc), followed by cement exposure. Industrial chemicals, after continuous exposure, may stay in the body as a *Dushivisha*.

The concept of *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* can be strongly correlated with *Vicharchika* and *Dadru* because most participants had a history of artificial poison (incompatible food, preservatives, beverages, tobacco chewing, smoking, medication apart from OTC, industrial exposure to various chemicals, etc.). Commentator Chakrapani asserts that *Dushivisha* as "*Kalantara Prakopi Visham*" means it is a type of *Visha* that aggravates after a long time in the body. When *Dushivisha* remains in the body, it disrupts the normal metabolism, leading to *Dhatu Dushti*, particularly affecting *Rakta Dhatu*⁶. This imbalance can cause various *Rakta Pradoshaja Vikaras*, including *Kushtha Roga*⁷. The current findings suggest that *Kritrima Visha* (Artificial poison) as *Dushivisha* may contribute to the development of *Vicharchika* and *Dadru*.

Conclusion:

The study was aimed to evaluate the association of exposure of *Kritrim Visha* as *Dushivisha* with *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* through an observational study design. After analysis and discussion, the following inferences can be drawn from the current study:

The association between the exposure to artificial poison and *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* was found statistically significant with odds ratio of 7.375 in 95% C.I. (4.39- 12.37). Also, association between the exposure to *Viruddhahara* and *Vicharchika* and/or *Dadru* was found statistically significant with odds

ratio of 4.992 in 95% C.I. (3.05- 8.16). Thus, we can conclude that continuous exposure to *Nidana* of *Kritrim Visha* as *Dushivisha* is responsible for the manifestation of skin disease.

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